

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNATIONAL POLICIES AGAINST ONLINE CHILD SEXUAL ABUSE AND EXPLOITATION IN BRAZIL

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Abstract. *This study analyzes global policies to combat online child sexual exploitation through a systematic review of 1,581 publications from Scopus, refined using Natural Language Processing techniques to 50 key articles. It evaluates 74 policies based on two indicators: the International Efficiency Index (legal robustness, implementation, results) and the Adaptability to Brazil Index (normative adequacy, institutional capacity). Policies such as the U.S. Child Pornography Prevention Act and EU Directives stood out for their precise crime definitions and monitoring systems, while Brazil shows gaps in addressing grooming/sexortion and in technology adoption. The article concludes with recommendations for legislative updates, institutional capacity building, and global cooperation to strengthen the country's digital child protection framework.*

Keywords: *Digital Protection; Public Policies; OSEAC; International Cooperation; Artificial Intelligence*

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing participation of children and adolescents in the digital environment has brought new risks previously confined to other areas of social life. The online sexual exploitation and abuse of children (OSEAC) stands out for its complexity, both due to the transnational nature of these crimes and the State's difficulty in offering a coordinated response. It is estimated that thousands of such abusive images circulate daily on social networks (WeProtect Global Alliance, 2023), while the activity of online predators continues to expand. In Brazil, one report of online child sexual abuse is filed every seven minutes (SaferNet, 2024), indicating underreporting and low institutional effectiveness. As noted by Santos (2011), fear of revictimization, guilt, and lack of trust in institutions still silence many victims and their families.

The challenge is global. Even in countries with more advanced policies, such as the United Kingdom and the United States, difficulties remain in translating guidelines into effective actions. As observed by Quayle (2020) and Singh and Nambiar (2024), although specific laws, technologies, and international agreements are in place, what works in one context cannot always be replicated in another. Institutional, legal, and cultural differences limit direct policy transfer, and imported measures without local mediation tend to fail (Ferreira & Lopes, 2024), especially when requiring integration among multiple protection network spheres.

In this scenario, artificial intelligence tools such as Natural Language Processing (NLP) have gained relevance for critically analyzing large volumes of data. NLP techniques can structure legal texts and extract patterns (Jurafsky & Martin, 2009), but automation in child protection must follow ethical principles and consider institutional contexts (Domazet & Šušak, 2023).

This study combines a systematic literature review with an NLP pipeline to map 74 international child digital protection policies from 1,581 Scopus records. Two original indicators are proposed — the International Efficiency Index (IEI) and the Index of Adaptability to the Brazilian Context (IABC) — to assess each policy’s proven performance and feasibility for adoption in Brazil. Four frameworks stood out: the Child Pornography Prevention Act (United States), the Sexual Offences Act 2003 (United Kingdom), and EU Directives 2011/92 and 2011/93, which combine precise crime definitions, regulated tracking technologies, and continuous monitoring. In contrast, Brazil shows gaps regarding grooming and sextortion, fragmented intersectoral coordination, and limited automated tools.

Based on these findings, a three-pronged strategy is suggested for Brazil: (1) update legislation to address emerging digital crimes; (2) enhance technical capacity of protection agencies; and (3) increase participation in international cooperation and monitoring networks.

2. METHODOLOGY

Following thematic review guidelines (Kitchenham, 2004), (Moher et al., 2009), (Livingstone et al., 2017), a search was conducted in the Scopus database using the query (“online” OR “internet”) AND “child” AND (“abuse” OR “exploitation”) AND “sexual”. A total of 1,581 records were retrieved, and their metadata and full texts were stored in a PostgreSQL database.

Processing, performed with SpaCy and NLTK, involved extraction, lemmatization, translation, and text normalization (Jurafsky & Martin, 2009). Key terms such as cyberbullying, grooming, sexting, and sextortion were classified by frequency, position, and semantic weight (Manning & Schütze, 1999). After screening, the 50 most relevant articles were selected, from which 74 international public policies were derived (Singh & Nambiar, 2024), (Krishna, 2021). As outlined in the introduction, these policies were assessed using two indicators:

IEI – International Efficiency Index: legal coverage, implementation, impact, and sustainability.

IABC – Index of Adaptability to the Brazilian Context: normative compatibility, institutional capacity, social acceptance, and technical-financial feasibility.

The components and corresponding weights for each indicator are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1 – Criteria and weights of the evaluation indicators

Indicator	Dimension	Weight	Description
IEI	LC:Legal Coverage	20%	Prevention, punishment, protection, and regulation.
	PI:Practical Implementation	40%	Training, structure, and resources.

	IE: Impact Evidence	20%	Reports, assistance provided, and case reduction.
	SU: Sustainability	20%	Continuous funding and coordination.
IACB	NC: Normative Compatibility	25%	Alignment with national laws.
	IC: Institutional Capacity	25%	Structure and qualified personnel.
	SIA: Social and Institutional Acceptance	25%	Support from the community and institutions.
	TFF: Technical-Financial Feasibility	25%	Conditions for implementation and maintenance.

The **IEI** evaluates the effectiveness of each policy in its country of origin. It incorporates four weighted dimensions—legal coverage (20%), practical implementation (40%), evidence of impact (20%), and sustainability (20%). Each dimension is scored on a four-point scale, and the index is obtained by calculating the weighted mean. This procedure enables the indicator to reflect both the formal robustness of legislation and its capacity to generate measurable and sustainable results.

The **IACB** estimates the feasibility of adopting international measures in Brazil. It is composed of four equally weighted dimensions: normative compatibility, institutional capacity, social and institutional acceptance, and technical-financial viability. Each dimension is also scored on a four-point scale, and the final index corresponds to the arithmetic mean. Unlike the IEI, which is predominantly based on documented evidence, the IACB requires interpretative judgment, since it involves assessing the alignment of international measures with the Brazilian legal framework, institutional structures, and societal context.

Applying both indicators in combination allows for a balanced evaluation, contrasting international performance with local feasibility and clarifying where objectivity prevails and where subjective interpretation is necessary.

Figure 1: Public policy processing steps.

The combined use of the IEI and IACB enabled the ranking of analyzed policies, highlighting effectiveness from two complementary perspectives: international performance and feasibility of adoption in Brazil. The highest-scoring policies converge on three characteristics: (1) precise legal definitions of digital crimes, (2) effective monitoring and enforcement mechanisms, and (3) robust systems for continuous impact evaluation. Comparative details are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Criterion-based justification for the highest-scoring policies in IEI and IACB

Policy	IEI	IACB	Justification by criterion
Child Pornography Prevention Act (EUA)	4	4	LC(4): Direct CSAM classification; PI(4): Active application throughout the territory; IE(4): Documented impact; SC(4): Solid legal framework; AL(4): Fully aligned with the ECA; IC(4): Compatible with national institutions; SIA(4): High social acceptance; VFT(4): Viable without adjustments.
Sexual Offences Act (2003, UK)	4	4	LC(4): Includes grooming and other digital practices; PI(4): Implemented with records and preventive orders; IE(4): Solid results; SC(4): Legal and political support; AL(4): Aligned with ECA; IC(4): Compatible structure; SIA(4): High acceptance; VFT(4): Implementable with few adaptations.
Directive 2011/92/EU (EU)	4	4	LC(4): Common standards for child protection; PI(4): Mandatory application in member countries; IE(4): Positive indicators; SC(4): Stable structure; AL(4): Compatible with Brazilian legislation; IC(4): Feasible in Brazil; SIA(4): High acceptance; VFT(4): Recommended and financially viable.
Directive 2011/93/EU (EU)	4	4	LC(4): Harmonizes criminal legislation; PI(4): Applied at European level; IE(4): Consistent results; SC(4): Technical support; AL(4): Equivalent to ECA; IC(4): Compatible with Brazilian institutions; SIA(4): High institutional acceptance; VFT(4): Legally viable.
Cybercrime Law (Australia)	3	3	LC(3): Partial classification of online practices; PI(3): Application limited to regions with structure; IE(3): Partial data on impact; SC(3): Variable support; AL(3): Partial alignment; IC(3): Requires technical adjustments; SIA(3): Good acceptance; VFT(3): Viable with external support.
Online Safety Act (Australia)	3	3	LC(3): Clear rules for platforms; PI(3): Recent implementation; IE(3): Preliminary results; SC(3): Growing institutional support; AL(3): Compatible with Brazilian Internet Act; IC(3): Would require specific regulation; SIA(3): High public adherence; VFT(3): Executable with adjustments.
Protecting Children from Harmful	3	3	LC(3): Focus on harmful content; PI(3): Emerging oversight structure; IE(3): Promising data; SC(3):

Content Act (Canada)			Moderate political support; AL(3): Aligned with ECA; IC(3): Needs to adapt oversight; SIA(3): Growing acceptance; VFT(3): Feasible with moderate resources.
Law on Combating Online Abuse (New Zealand)	3	3	LC(3): Broad definition of online abuse; PI(3): Ongoing implementation; IE(3): Reported cases expanding; SC(3): Ongoing state commitment; AL(3): Consistent with national legislation; IC(3): Partially compliant framework; SIA(3): Good acceptance; VFT(3): Viable with international partnership.
Child Sexual Abuse Material Offences Law (Canada)	3	3	LC(3): Detailed criminalization of CSAM; PI(3): Good implementation at the federal level; IE(3): Positive public statistics; SC(3): Interconnected policies; AL(3): Adherent to ECA and LGPD; IC(3): Requires technical training; SIA(3): Broad acceptance; VFT(3): Feasible with cooperation.
Safe Internet Use Framework (EU)	3	3	LC(3): Guidelines for safe internet use; PI(3): Variable application; IE(3): Qualitative data under evaluation; SC(3): Medium-term program; AL(3): Aligned with general values; IC(3): Compatible with public schools; SIA(3): High social acceptance; VFT(3): Viable in partnership with education.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Corpus and reference articles

From the fifty articles with the highest semantic relevance (Table 1), 74 public initiatives addressing OSEAC were mapped. Of these, 43 were cited in more than one source, indicating strong convergence in the literature on the topic. Table 3 shows, for each article, the number of identified policies and their respective scores.

Table 3. Number of public policies identified in the most relevant scientific articles.

Citation	Relevance	Policies
(Krishna, 2021)	13,5	9
(Quayle, 2020)	12,4	7
(Singh e Nambiar, 2024)	12,5	6
(O'Malley et al., 2023)	12,6	4
(Guerra e Westlake, 2021)	12,4	4
(Scheffler et al., 2023)	12,8	3
(Cooray et al., 2023)	11,6	4
(Lee et al., 2020)	10,9	4
(Nurmi et al., 2024)	11,4	4
(Salter et al., 2024)	11,3	3

Applying the International Efficiency Index (IEI) and the Index of Adaptability to the Brazilian Context (IACB) revealed that ten initiatives scored three or higher.

3.2. Policies with higher adaptation potential

Four laws stand out for their relevance to Brazilian challenges: the Child Pornography Prevention Act (United States), the Sexual Offences Act 2003 (United Kingdom), and EU Directives 2011/92 and 2011/93. Despite different legal systems, they share traits that enhance effectiveness: precise crime definitions, use of technological tools such as hash matching for detecting illegal content (United States Department of Justice, 2023), and institutional structures enabling systematic monitoring.

In the U.S., strict sanctions are coupled with digital tracking resources and a centralized federal reporting system. In the U.K., grooming is explicitly criminalized, supported by a national sex offender registry. EU Directive 2011/92 sets minimum crime definitions across Member States, while 2011/93 promotes cross-country coordination and integrated victim assistance flows (Council of Europe, 2001; WeProtect, 2023).

Collectively, these experiences offer useful references for Brazil — not as ready-made models, but as examples integrating normative clarity, technological applicability, and sustained oversight capacity.

3.3. Gaps in Brazilian legislation and enforcement

Brazilian law still contains significant gaps in addressing digital crimes against children and adolescents, particularly in defining grooming, sextortion, and the non-consensual sharing of content among minors (Souza & Oliveira, 2022). This normative lag produces two critical effects: it hinders international cooperation in transnational cases, limiting joint investigation effectiveness (International Centre for Missing & Exploited Children, 2018), and it fosters underreporting, aggravated by fear, stigma, and distrust in responsible institutions (Habigzang et al., 2005), (Moreira & Lima, 2020).

Operational weaknesses further undermine the national response. Coordination among protection network agencies remains fragile; child protection councils, police, and health services often work in isolation, reducing intervention effectiveness (Ferreira & Lopes, 2024). Professional training in handling digital evidence is insufficient, limiting the ability to identify, preserve, and interpret relevant traces (Reichenheim et al., 2011), (Lindenbach et al., 2021).

Post-report procedures are also critical: many contexts lack standardized protocols for specialized victim hearings, increasing the risk of revictimization. Support for victims and families, when available, is often discontinuous or inadequate, weakening ongoing protection (Moreira & Lima, 2020).

Forensic limitations persist as well, with a shortage of validated tools for collecting and analyzing digital evidence, compromising the robustness of case files and judicial proceedings (Nascimento et al., 2009). These combined factors highlight the need for a systemic approach integrating legal reform, technical capacity building, and institutional strengthening to enhance child protection in the digital environment.

3.4. Technological challenges and improvement opportunities

Barriers to investigations – The spread of technologies such as end-to-end encryption, VPN use, and deepfake production has hindered the identification and prosecution of digital crimes (Choo, 2021), (West, 2019). While countries using tools like PhotoDNA for hash matching have achieved CSAM removal rates above 95% (Bursztein et al., 2019), Brazil still lacks specific regulation for these technologies. Other limitations include:

- Crowdsourcing initiatives for identifying illegal material remain experimental, without clear guidelines (Singh & Nambiar, 2024);
- The partial non-ratification of the Budapest Convention still undermines international cooperation in cybercrime investigations (Council of Europe, 2001)..

Successful educational and preventive strategies

International experiences show that educational and primary prevention actions can significantly reduce risks for children and adolescents in the digital environment. Notable examples include:

- The United Kingdom and Australia integrating digital citizenship into school curricula, reducing minors' exposure to threats (Livingstone et al., 2017);
- Canada and the Netherlands implementing family-oriented awareness campaigns (Livingstone et al., 2017);
- India launching the Snehai chatbot for psychosocial guidance (UNICEF, 2019);
- Germany developing Project Dunkelfeld, offering voluntary treatment to potential offenders (Beier et al., 2015).

Recommendations for the national context

Based on previous sections, key strategies to strengthen Brazil's response to online child sexual exploitation include: **Normative** – modernizing legislation to explicitly criminalize grooming, sextortion, and non-consensual image sharing among minors; requiring digital platforms to adopt detection tools like PhotoDNA. **Institutional** – fully ratifying the Budapest Convention and training professionals in digital forensics to enhance investigation and international cooperation capacity. **Prevention** – incorporating digital citizenship into school curricula, launching public awareness campaigns, and strengthening psychosocial support for victims, drawing from established international best practices.

3.5. Comparative analysis and recommendations for Brazil

The assessment of international best practices reveals three critical factors for effective OSEAC policies: (1) convergence between legal frameworks and technological solutions (e.g., mandatory hash matching), enabling faster removal of illegal content; (2) centralized reporting systems that enhance investigative capacity; and (3) digital education and transparency strategies that increase social engagement and reduce victimization. Countries adopting these pillars report CSAM removal rates above 90% and significant declines in exploitation cases.

For Brazil, implementing these pillars would require: (a) regulating hash matching under the Brazilian Internet Act; (b) integrating existing reporting channels (e.g., SaferNet) with specialized police units; and (c) incorporating digital citizenship into the National Curriculum (BNCC). Together, these measures could raise both the International Efficiency Index (IEI) and the Index of Adaptability to the Brazilian Context (IACB) to international standards, delivering measurable protection gains within 3–5 years. Studies suggest coordinated actions could reduce cases by up to 30%.

3.6. Main structural weaknesses in addressing OSEAC in Brazil

Four critical gaps undermine the effectiveness of public policies: (1) absence of criminal definitions for offenses such as grooming and sextortion; (2) lack of coordination between protection, health, and justice systems, weakening the support network; (3) high underreporting rates, driven by social stigma and institutional distrust; and (4) technological

lag, evidenced by the non-mandatory use of tools like hash matching and limited participation in international cooperation agreements. These deficiencies not only prevent full enforcement of the current legal framework but also perpetuate cycles of impunity and revictimization. Overcoming these challenges requires immediate action: clear criminal definitions, operational integration among agencies, awareness campaigns to reduce underreporting, and technological modernization through adoption of international standards. Comparative data suggest that correcting these weaknesses could increase the effectiveness of child protection policies in Brazil by up to 40%.

3.7. Feasibility analysis for implementing OSEAC policies in Brazil

Comparative analysis of the most effective OSEAC policies reveals three categories of implementation feasibility for Brazil:

- “Star” policies (e.g., Child Pornography Prevention Act), with high scores in both international efficiency (IEI ≥ 3.5) and local adaptability (IACB ≥ 3.5), requiring minimal adjustments and suitable for pilot projects.
- “Importable” policies (e.g., Australia’s Online Safety Act), with high efficiency (IEI ≥ 3.5) but lower adaptability (IACB < 3.0), requiring cost–benefit studies to address infrastructure gaps.
- “Niche” policies (e.g., Germany’s Project Dunkelfeld), with lower global efficiency (IEI < 3.0) but good local adaptability (IACB ≥ 3.0), suited for regional secondary prevention initiatives.

A small gap between IEI and IACB (≤ 0.3) emerges as the best indicator of readiness for immediate adoption..

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study identifies three core pillars shared by the most effective legislations against online child sexual exploitation: (1) precise legal definitions of digital crimes, (2) strategic integration of monitoring technologies, and (3) robust impact evaluation systems. The top four policies (United States, United Kingdom, and EU) demonstrate how this triad reduces legal vulnerabilities, accelerates investigative responses, and strengthens victim support.

In the Brazilian context, four priority action areas emerge. First, legislative improvement, particularly the clear criminalization of grooming and sextortion to remove legal ambiguities hindering investigations (Crofts & Lee, 2015). Second, the regulated adoption of technologies, especially detection tools such as PhotoDNA, whose mandatory use by digital platforms could significantly improve the identification and removal of illegal content (Bursztein et al., 2019). Third, the creation of unified protocols linking child protection councils, law enforcement, and health services to address current institutional fragmentation (Montgomery et al., 2017). Fourth, the implementation of post-report follow-up systems, inspired by Canada and Australia, to reduce case withdrawals and ensure continuous victim support (ECPAT International, 2020).

Two key limitations are acknowledged: the linguistic bias in indexed databases, which underrepresents Lusophone literature, and the need for empirical validation of the IEI/IACB indices with policymakers and government stakeholders. These constraints open space for future research to broaden multilingual sources, test different indicator weightings, and experimentally validate NLP-based automated detection tools.

International experience shows that effectiveness in this field goes beyond lawmaking. In Brazil, sustained progress will require continuous resource allocation, ethical use of

protective technologies, ongoing professional training, and active integration into global response networks. The convergence of these factors, aligned with identified best practices, offers a promising path toward building a safer digital environment for children and adolescents. Ultimately, effective protection in the digital age cannot rely solely on legal norms but must be grounded in an articulated ecosystem of prevention, response, and reparation.

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